

Predicting EU orchard farmers' adoption intentions for pesticide-reducing innovations using an extended theory of planned behavior

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ABSTRACT

Reducing synthetic pesticide use is central to the EU Green Deal. However, with legislative progress stalled, farmers increasingly bear the responsibility for implementing pesticide reduction. This highlights the need to understand how decisions are made and what shapes farmers' intentions to adopt technologies that reduced pesticide use, particularly in orchard systems where pesticide dependence remains high despite the availability of promising alternatives. This study examines stakeholder roles in orchard pest management, identifies key drivers of farmers' adoption intentions, and develops a tool to predict adoption likelihood. A mixed-methods approach was applied, combining expert interviews (n = 16) and a structured survey of orchard farmers (n = 354). We extended the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) by incorporating three additional constructs: perceived cost, relative advantage of current practices, and perceived ease of use, all based on established behavioral theories. Results show that decision-making involves multiple stakeholders and is influenced by factors such as farm size, ownership structure, and external pressures. Meanwhile, structural equation modeling shows that attitudes and perceived ease of use significantly boost adoption intentions. In contrast, perceived cost and the relative advantage of current practices serve as barriers. Subjective norms and perceived behavioral control were not significant predictors. Based on these findings, a web-based adoption intention predictive tool was developed to support stakeholders in assessing adoption likelihood. The study offers practical insights for reducing adoption barriers, strengthening positive attitudes toward innovation, and supporting sustainable pest management in orchard systems.

1. Introduction

Pesticides are extensively used in global agriculture to protect crop health, particularly in commercial farming (Crall et al., 2018; Hallmann et al., 2014; McGinley et al., 2023; Woodcock et al., 2017; Yamamuro et al., 2019). Since their widespread adoption in the mid-20th century, plant protection products, commonly known as pesticides, have become indispensable in global agriculture, playing a critical role in protecting crops from pests and diseases (Schneider et al., 2023; Tudi et al., 2021). Several agronomic studies suggest that in the absence of pesticides, crop losses could be considerable, with estimates of up to 78 % for fruits, 54 % for vegetables, and 32 % for cereals (Cai, 2008; Lazarević-Pašti et al., 2025; Tudi et al., 2021). Other research similarly indicates that

pesticides safeguard roughly one-third of global agricultural production (Oirdi et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2011).

However, the excessive use of synthetic pesticides poses serious environmental and societal challenges, including biodiversity loss, ground and surface water pollution, and health risks to humans and animals (Finger and Möhring, 2024; Tang et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2025). Concerns about pesticide use in European agriculture have resurfaced, with current levels increasingly regarded as unsustainable due to their environmental and economic impact. This has prompted renewed policy debate and proposals for stricter regulation (Schneider et al., 2023; Finger and Möhring, 2024; Finger et al., 2024). In response, in 2020, the European Commission (EC) set an ambitious target to halve synthetic pesticide use by 2030 (Gohin, 2024; Wesseler, 2022).

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However, the proposed legislation, the Sustainable Use Regulation (SUR) published in 2022 has since failed to materialize due to strong farmer and political resistance. As a result, the responsibility for reducing synthetic pesticide use now rests largely on voluntary actions on the part of farmers. This raises a critical question: to what extent are farmers willing to adopt alternative practices that reduce reliance on synthetic pesticides, and what factors shape their decision-making?

Vineyards and olive groves are among the most pesticide-dependent crop sectors in Europe, particularly in the Euro-Mediterranean region (Chen et al., 2022; Rivas et al., 2021). Despite their significant economic, nutritional, and cultural value, these crops are highly susceptible to pests and disease attacks, requiring pesticide applications at various production stages to meet consumption and industrial demands (Bremmer et al., 2021; Liviz et al., 2025; Schneider et al., 2023). Synthetic pesticides, including fungicides, insecticides, herbicides, and bactericides are commonly applied throughout the ripening process to protect fruits from infestation. However, several studies have shown that excessive pesticide use in vineyards and olive groves can lead to residue accumulation in fruits and byproducts such as wine and olive oil. Additionally, it can contaminate surface waters, posing serious health and environmental risks (Teixeira et al., 2021; Schiano et al., 2024; Fernández-García et al., 2024).

Amid the EU's push for pesticide reduction under the Green Deal, a range of pesticide-reducing innovations have emerged in vine and olive cultivation. These innovations relate to technologies and practices designed to lower or optimize the use of synthetic plant protection products while maintaining crop health and productivity. Examples include resistant crop varieties that reduce the need for chemical applications (Casanova-Gascón et al., 2019; Salmon et al., 2018), precision technologies such as ground robotics and variable-rate application guided by canopy characterization (Salas et al., 2024; Upadhyay et al., 2024; Ehrampoosh et al., 2025), bioinsecticides and biocontrol agents that provide sustainable pest control (Alimadadi et al., 2023; Godana et al., 2020), and integrated pest management measures such as ground cover crops that foster natural predators (Álvarez et al., 2021; Lantero et al., 2023; Byrne et al., 2025). Depending on the extent of adoption, these alternatives have been shown to reduce pesticide use in orchards¹ by 40–80 % without compromising yields (García-Ruiz et al., 2023; Peshin and Zhang, 2014).

Beyond their technical and environmental benefits, these innovations represent a potential entry point for conventional growers into broader transitions toward sustainable and agroecological practices in the orchard sector. Prior studies highlight the importance of institutional factors such as access to training, credit, and policy support, as well as risk perception and farm structure (Alphonse et al., 2024; Ataei et al., 2023). Recent qualitative work further emphasizes the role of personal motivation, ecological values, and pivotal life events in shaping farmers' engagement with agroecological practices (Markiewicz-Keszycka et al., 2025). These findings suggest that transition pathways are shaped by a dynamic interaction between external conditions and internal dispositions. Building on this work, the present study deepens our understanding of the behavioral factors that influence such transitions among conventional orchard farmers.

Previous research has improved our understanding of farmers' willingness to adopt specific pesticide-reducing technologies. For example, Feisthauer et al. (2023) found that pro-environmental attitudes, rather than subsidies or nudges, drive the adoption of smart weeding technologies among German crop farmers. Similarly, Despotović et al. (2019) and Ataei et al. (2021) reported that social and moral norms, along with perceived behavioral control, significantly influence the adoption intentions of tomato farmers with regard to integrated pest management and green pesticides. Research on precision irrigation

adoption in olive groves and cotton farms in Greece also highlights that environmental consciousness is the strongest predictor of adoption, followed by perceived economic benefits, behavioral control, and compatibility (Kakkavou et al., 2024). A weight and meta-analysis study by Neves et al. (2022) further synthesizes these findings, emphasizing that attitude, perceived benefits, personal norms, and incentives act as the best predictors of behavioral intentions with regard to sustainable technology adoption. However, despite these insights, research remains fragmented, often focusing on single technologies rather than providing a comprehensive understanding of farmers' decision-making processes regarding pesticide-reducing innovations. Moreover, most studies have focused on arable crops, with limited attention being paid to pesticide-intensive perennial cropping systems such as those that can be used in vineyards and olive orchards, where adoption could generate substantial environmental benefits. To the best of the authors' knowledge, only a limited number of studies have holistically examined farmers' decision-making processes and adoption intentions regarding pesticide-reducing technologies, particularly in EU vineyards and olive orchards, where pesticide use remains high despite the development of promising pesticide-reducing innovations.

Although regulatory measures could accelerate pesticide reduction, political obstacles, such as the EU parliament rejection of the Sustainable Use Regulation (SUR) proposal in November 2023 and its subsequent indefinite withdrawal in February 2025 (Finger, 2024; Finger et al., 2024) currently limit this pathway. At the same time, farm-level production dynamics reinforce the urgency of change. Climate change involving rising temperatures and shifting pathogen dynamics has intensified pest and disease pressures in Mediterranean vineyards and olive groves (Caffarra et al., 2012; Elad and Pertot, 2014). Farmers relying solely on conventional chemical controls often respond with more frequent and intensive pesticide applications (Lechenet et al., 2017), which further entrenches dependence on synthetic inputs. Thus, while EU regulation could have provided the necessary momentum for reducing pesticide use, changing conditions at the farm level, driven by climate change and shifting pest dynamics, are making the adoption of pesticide-reducing innovations increasingly essential. Understanding farmers' decision-making and adoption intentions is therefore critical to supporting the transition toward more sustainable pest management practices. This study investigates the behavioral factors influencing farmers' adoption of pesticide-reducing technologies, providing valuable insights to support the transition toward more sustainable pest management. The study addresses three key questions: 1) What drives farmers' decision-making in terms of pest and disease treatment and technology adoption? 2) What factors influence farmers' intentions to adopt pesticide-reducing innovations? and 3) How can these insights be used to predict the adoption intentions on the part of target farmers?

The research is driven by several EU Horizon 2020-funded research and innovation projects aimed at addressing sustainable food production and the needs of end-users, including farmers, in the agricultural sector. One such initiative is NOVATERRA, a project focused on reducing the negative impact of pesticides in Mediterranean olive groves and vineyards (<https://www.novaterraproject.eu/>). Under the NOVATERRA project a range of innovative technologies and practices, including the use of smart mapping tools, robotic weed control, bio-solutions, and cover crops with floral margins have been proposed, with demonstrated effectiveness in reducing pesticide use in orchards (Salas et al., 2024). While these technologies hold great promise, their successful adoption by orchard farmers is critical to achieving sustainable pesticide use in the sector. Understanding the factors that drive or hinder such adoption will help shape policies and strategies that support sustainable pest management in European orchards.

Different theories, in the form of those relating to the diffusion of innovations (Dewi et al., 2023), the technology acceptance model (Flett et al., 2004), social cognitive theory (Gao and Arbuckle, 2022), the theoretical framework of acceptability (Thomas et al., 2023), and multinomial regression models (Asante et al., 2024) depending on

¹ For clarity, following Tonolli et al. (2024), in this study we use the term "orchard" to refer to vineyards (viticulture) and olive groves (oliviculture).

context, have been employed to explain farmers' adoption intentions with regard to new agricultural technologies (Karbo et al., 2024; Olum et al., 2020). Among these, the theory of planned behavior (TPB), a reasoned action approach that emphasizes attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, has been particularly effective in explaining farmers' decision-making processes (Garmendia-Lemus et al., 2024; Sok et al., 2021). Building on its strong theoretical foundations, we extend the TPB framework by integrating three additional constructs based on established behavioral and technology adoption theories to provide a more comprehensive analysis of farmers' adoption intentions.

The research follows a three-step qualitative-quantitative approach: (1), identifying key factors and actors in the decision-making process regarding pest management and related technology adoption through the use of expert interviews; (2), refining and applying an extended TPB model via a structured farmer survey to predict their adoption intentions; and (3), developing a predictive tool that assesses the likelihood of farmers adopting pesticide-reducing innovations, as summarized in Fig. 1.

The structure of the paper is as follows: Section 2 outlines the theoretical framework based on the Theory of Planned Behavior, presents the study's hypotheses, and describes the methods used for the empirical analysis. Section 3 presents the findings, followed by Section 4, which discusses the results in depth. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Theoretical and research model

Adoption is the decision to make full use of an innovation as the best course of action. It involves integrating new ideas, products, or technologies into existing systems as intended by the developers (Rogers, 1983a). Adoption intention can be defined as the readiness or willingness of the target population to embrace a particular innovation. The successful implementation of agricultural innovations depends

significantly on farmers' acceptance and adoption of the target innovation or alternative practices, which in turn are believed to be strongly determined by their behavioral intentions. Consequently, numerous studies have examined the factors influencing farmers' intentions to adopt pro-environmental technologies and practices (Castillo et al., 2021; Colin et al., 2022; Garmendia-Lemus et al., 2024; Zeng et al., 2020).

Among the various approaches used to study adoption intentions, the TPB model remains one of the most powerful, robust and widely-applied theoretical bases (Bagheri et al., 2019; Sok et al., 2021). As an extension of the theory of reasoned action, the TPB was developed to address behaviors over which individuals may have limited control (Ajzen, 1991). The classical TPB model posits that an individual's intention to perform a certain behavior or practice, which is central to the model, is determined by their attitudes toward the behavior under consideration, their perceived behavioral control, and subjective norms (Ajzen, 1991; Ajzen et al., 2004). Thus, intention reflects an individual's motivation or conscious decision to exert effort, thereby influencing the likelihood of behavior enactment (Conner and Armitage, 1998). In terms of our study, the predictive power of the TPB model has been validated in various studies on farmer adaptation behaviors, including adaptation to natural disasters, climate change, adoption of irrigation technologies, and engagement in sustainable agricultural practices (Dong et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2020), which is why this model is taken as the theoretical foundation for this work.

Nonetheless, the TPB model has certain limitations, such as an exclusive focus on beliefs and self-interest, and the neglect of moral norms (Zhang et al., 2020). To improve its predictive power, it is beneficial to integrate additional constructs based on both theoretical and practical considerations. This is because, in the context of pesticide-reducing and sustainable pest-control technologies, identifying and incorporating these influential factors is crucial. The next section provides the expanded TPB framework that was used in our study, which is based on established theories and expert surveys.

Fig. 1. Summarized steps used in the study.

2.2. Extended TPB model and hypotheses

The core of the TPB model proposes that an individual's intention (INT) can be predicted with a high degree of accuracy from attitudes (ATD) towards a certain behavior, perceived behavioral control (PBC), and subjective norms (SN) (Ajzen, 1991, 2002).

Attitude refers to the degree to which a person has a favorable (positive) or unfavorable (negative) evaluation of engaging in a certain practice or behavior. An individual's attitude toward a particular behavior depends on the overall evaluation of that behavior and a belief in its desirable outcomes; thus, a positive ATD toward a particular behavior can lead to a greater intention to perform that behavior (Gao et al., 2017; Tan et al., 2017). Considering alternative pesticide-reducing innovations, orchard farmers will have adoption intentions if they believe that using them would have favorable or better outcomes than exist at present.

Perceived behavioral control is the perceived difficulty or ease of performing a specific behavior and is used as an approximation of one's actual behavior control (Wang et al., 2023). Specifically, PBC represents individuals' engagement in a given behavior on the basis of their belief in the possibility of accessing the required resources and opportunities (Rezaei et al., 2019). Generally, farmers with higher control capacities tend to be the ones to adopt relevant measures (Savari and Gharechae, 2020).

Subjective norms refers to the personal perception of behavior under the influence of other people's attitudes. SN therefore shows how individuals weigh the expectations of "important others" or social expectations (Castillo et al., 2021). It is usually expected that high cognition of the SN can increase behavioral intentions (Wang et al., 2023).

Following Rezaei et al. (2019) and Wang et al. (2023), we assume that intentions provide a good indication of farmers' behaviors (i.e., the adoption of pesticide-reducing technologies in this case) since intentions are strong predictors of pro-environmental behavior. Therefore, in the light of the original TPB framework, we formulate the following hypotheses:

H1. Farmers' attitudes towards pesticide reduction have a positive effect on the intention to adopt pesticide-reducing innovations.

H2. Farmers' perceived behavioral control has a positive effect on the intention to adopt pesticide-reducing innovations.

H3. Farmers' subjective norms have a positive effect on the intention to adopt pesticide-reducing innovations.

Although the classical TPB assumes that attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control are sufficient predictors of intention, this assumption has been relaxed over time. Ajzen and Klobas (2013) emphasized that the TPB serves as an open and flexible framework in which additional predictors may be incorporated when they meaningfully increase the explained variance in behavioral intention. Following this reasoning, we extend the TPB by including three constructs grounded in established theories: perceived cost, conceptualized as response costs within the Protection Motivation Theory (PMT) (Rogers, 1975, Rogers, 1983b); relative advantage, drawn from Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DOI) (Rogers, 2003) and the perceived usefulness dimension of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989); and perceived ease of use, also rooted in TAM and aligned with the diffusion of innovation concept of complexity. These constructs provide a strong theoretical basis for explaining orchard farmers' adoption intentions regarding pesticide-reducing innovations.

2.2.1. Perceived cost of pesticide-reducing innovations

The first additional construct is the perceived cost (PC) of pesticide-reducing innovations. Previous studies show that farmers often face economic uncertainties when deciding between new or conventional practices, with barriers such as costs and their implications for future

operations (Gao and Arbuckle, 2022; Marra et al., 2003). Orchard production requires considerable investment in pest and disease control to maintain productivity. Any perceived costs linked to alternative innovations, particularly where subsidies are lacking, can directly affect operating expenses and economic goals. This raises risk perceptions and influences farmers' willingness to move away from established methods (Chèze et al., 2020; Liu and Liu, 2024).

Within the PMT (Rogers, 1975, Rogers, 1983b), such costs are conceptualized as response costs, one of the key elements of the coping appraisal process. Coping appraisal reflects an individual's evaluation of whether they have the ability, resources, and capacity to perform a recommended action. Response costs include the financial outlay, time, training, and effort required to perform the recommended behavior. High response costs reduce coping appraisal, which weakens the intention to act, even when perceived efficacy and self-efficacy are strong (McLeod et al., 2015). In the case of orchards, farmers may view pesticide-reducing technologies as too expensive, labor-intensive, or complex to implement without external support. Following this reasoning, PC in the extended TPB framework is defined as the extent to which farmers consider pesticide-reducing innovations to be disadvantageous relative to their current pest control practices. This leads to the formulation of a fourth hypothesis:

H4. Perceived additional costs for pesticide-reducing innovations negatively affect the intention of farmers with regard to adopting such innovations.

2.2.2. Relative advantage of existing methods

The second additional construct is the relative advantage (RA) of existing methods compared to pesticide-reducing innovations. In DOI theory (Rogers, 2003), adoption decisions depend on how individuals evaluate the superiority of one option over another. Relative advantage is typically used to assess whether an innovation is perceived to be better than current practices, but in this study, it is viewed as the reverse: farmer assess whether their established pest control methods are more effective, efficient, or valuable than the new alternatives. This perspective is particularly relevant in the orchard sector, where long-standing practices are embedded in farm routines and reinforced by past success. If growers believe that their existing methods provide greater benefits or are more reliable, the incentive to adopt new technologies diminishes. Similar to perceived usefulness in the TAM (Davis, 1989), this construct captures the comparative evaluation that directly shapes adoption intention. When existing practices are judged as superior, pesticide-reducing innovations are perceived to lack relative advantage, thereby reducing farmers' willingness to adopt them. This leads to the formulation of a fifth hypothesis:

H5. Farmers' perception that their existing methods have greater relative advantage negatively affects their intention to adopt pesticide-reducing innovations

2.2.3. Perceived ease of use of pesticide-reducing innovations

The final additional construct is the perceived ease of use (PEU) of pesticide-reducing innovations. The TAM posits that the adoption of novel systems depends not only on usefulness, but also on whether individuals believe the technology is simple to understand and apply with minimal effort (Davis, 1989). Complex or time-consuming practices create barriers to uptake, even when benefits are clear (Gomes and Reidsma, 2021). This aligns with Rogers's DOI theory, which identifies complexity as a critical factor shaping adoption rates (Rogers, 2003). For farmers, innovations that appear too demanding in terms of training, labor, or management adjustments may be rejected, whereas innovations perceived as straightforward to integrate are more readily accepted. Familiarity plays a role here, as repeated exposure reduces uncertainty and lowers perceived complexity, consistent with the mere exposure effect (Zajonc, 1968). For example, farmers with prior knowledge of bio-solutions or precision spraying tools may find them

easier to adopt than those encountering them for the first time. This leads to the formulation of a sixth hypothesis:

H6. Farmers' perception of greater ease of use of pesticide-reducing innovations based on their familiarity positively affects their intention to adopt them.

The extended TPB framework integrates three theoretically grounded constructs, namely perceived cost (from PMT), relative advantage (from DOI and perceived usefulness in TAM), and perceived ease of use (from TAM and the DOI concept of complexity), as summarized in Fig. 2. The constructs were incorporated as direct predictors of adoption intention to capture the economic, comparative advantage, and practical dimensions influencing farmers' behavioral decisions. Each determinant of intention was modeled as a latent variable measured by multiple observed indicators. In total, 23 items were used to operationalize the seven constructs: adoption intention, attitude, perceived behavioral control, subjective norms, perceived cost, relative advantage, and perceived ease of use (see Appendix A).

2.3. Study design

The study follows a structured, sequential three-step mixed-method approach that integrates qualitative and quantitative methods (Fig. 1). First, semi-structured interviews with industry experts (n = 16) were used to identify key actors and the factors influencing orchard farmers' pesticide use decisions, providing foundational insights into their adoption decision-making process. These findings guided the design of a structured farmer survey based on the extended TPB model, allowing for a quantitative assessment of the factors shaping farmers' adoption intentions. Finally, the results from the extended TPB model were used as baseline data to develop a predictive tool that estimates the likelihood of a farmer adopting pesticide-reducing technologies. This near-iterative step ensures that each stage builds on the previous one, resembling a machine-learning pipeline where each step refines and enhances the next, leading to a more robust, inclusive, and data-driven conclusion.

2.3.1. Survey design and data collection

The study was carried out in five Euro-Mediterranean countries: France, Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain. These countries are among the largest producers of grapes and olives in Europe. The target population was conventional orchard farmers who use synthetic pesticides in their pest management practices. The data design followed a multi-stage process. In the first stage, 16 expert stakeholders from the orchard sector were identified through the NOVATERRA stakeholder network. Eight represented vineyards and eight represented olive groves. They included farm managers, association leaders, researchers, farm technicians, and practicing farmers. The experts participated in open-ended interviews that explored decision-making in pest management. The interviews focused on questions such as: *Who selects pesticides for orchard farms? Who decides whether new treatments should be adopted? What role do farmers play in selecting pest control technologies? What factors influence the adoption of new pest treatment methods?*

Insights from these interviews were combined with evidence from the literature (Garmendia-Lemus et al., 2024; Rezaei et al., 2019; Savari and Gharechaei, 2020; Sok et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2023) to design the survey questionnaire for farmers. The questionnaire was structured in two parts. The first part assessed farmers' adoption intentions through constructs based on the extended TPB. The second part gathered structural and socio-demographic information. To ensure contextual understanding, farmers were also presented with four examples of emerging pesticide-reducing innovations that represent precision farming, robotics, biosolutions, and cover crops. Each example included information on costs, benefits, and application in orchards with image and video demonstrations.

The questionnaire was drafted in English and then translated into French, Greek, Italian, Portuguese, and Spanish by sector experts who were also native speakers. This ensured both linguistic and technical accuracy. A pretest with 25 orchard farmers from across the five countries was conducted to assess item clarity, consistency, and reliability. Based on farmer feedback and initial psychometric checks, minor adjustments were made to refine the instrument. The final survey required

Fig. 2. The theoretical framework and hypotheses of the extended theory of planned behavior. Note: TAM-Technology Acceptance Model; MEE-Mere Exposure Effect.

approximately 6–8 minutes to complete and was administered in February 2024 through the QualtricsSM platform, an online survey tool that allows respondents to complete questionnaires securely via a web link.

Participants were recruited through stakeholder workshops and meetings organized under the EU Horizon 2020 NOVATERRA project, which brought together farmers, representatives of associations, researchers, and other stakeholders in the vineyard and olive sectors. Farmers attending these events, held in each of the five countries, were invited to complete the survey. To extend participation beyond these events, respondents were encouraged to share the survey link within their cooperatives and networks. This peer-referral process, used alongside direct recruitment at project events, helped broaden participation while maintaining a focus on the intended population of orchard farmers. Screening questions were applied to ensure that only conventional farmers were included in the final sample.

In total, 362 responses were collected across the five countries. After data cleaning, 354 valid and complete responses were retained for analysis. Ethical approval was obtained from the CREDA Ethical Committee (Approval No. 002–24) and the NOVATERRA project, and was in compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR). Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents. The socio-demographic and selected farm characteristics of the sample are presented in Table 1.

2.3.2. Construct measurement and validation

The latent constructs of the extended TPB model are multidimensional and could not be adequately represented by single indicators. To ensure reliable measurement, multi-item scales were adapted from previously-validated instruments in environmental behavior, agricultural innovation, and pro-environmental psychology. Each construct was carefully reviewed and the items reworded to reflect the context of pesticide-reducing innovations among orchard farmers across the five study countries. A reflective measurement approach was adopted, whereby the latent constructs are considered independent of individual

Table 1
Sample characteristics of the surveyed farmers (n = 354).

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Country	Greece	31	8.8 %
	France	29	8.2 %
	Italy	36	10.2 %
	Portugal	123	34.7 %
	Spain	135	38.1 %
Gender	Male	271	76.6 %
	Female	72	20.2 %
	Non-binary/Not declared	11	3.1 %
Age	18–34 years	56	15.7 %
	35–44 years	65	18.4 %
	45–54 years	101	28.6 %
	55–64 years	90	25.3 %
	65+ years	42	12.0 %
Education level	Primary school	11	3.2 %
	Secondary school	45	12.8 %
	Postsecondary studies	114	31.9 %
	University degree (Bachelor's)	91	25.8 %
	Postgraduate degree (Master/PhD)	93	26.3 %
Orchard type	Vineyard	272	76.7 %
	Olive grove	82	23.3 %
Farm size	Less than 5 ha	261	73.7 %
	Between 5 and 20 ha	67	19.9 %
	More than 20 ha	26	7.3 %
Effectiveness of current methods	Not effective	7	2.1 %
	Slightly effective	8	2.3 %
	Moderately effective	62	17.5 %
	Highly effective	210	59.1 %
	Extremely effective	67	18.9 %

Source: Farmer survey by authors

indicators, and items can be used interchangeably (Hair et al., 2013). All measurement items were derived from established scales used in previous behavioral research and refined to align with the objectives of this study. The adaptations focused on aligning item wording with farmers' decision-making processes while maintaining conceptual equivalence across contexts.

In total, 23 items were used to measure the seven constructs, including the endogenous variable (adoption intention), on a seven-point Likert scale ranging from “strongly disagree” (1) to “strongly agree” (7). To ensure content validity, the draft instrument was reviewed by experts and practitioners involved in orchard pest management, followed by a pretest with 25 farmers from the five countries. Feedback from the pretest led to minor refinements in wording to improve clarity and contextual relevance without altering the conceptual meaning. The final set of items, together with their corresponding constructs and adapted sources, is presented in Appendix A in the supplementary material.

2.3.3. Data analysis

The study employed the structural equation modelling (SEM) technique, a robust method for analyzing complex cause-effect relationships in TPB studies and in adoption research (Garmendia-Lemus et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2023). Preliminary tests assessed the suitability of the data for SEM, including normality via skewness and multicollinearity, based on criteria proposed by Grewal et al. (2004). Based on Yamane's (1973) method of sample determination, as well as the required minimum sample size for SEM, a sample size of 240 was deemed to be needed for the analysis, indicating that our 354 sample was adequate (Kline, 2023). The descriptive analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS, and PLS-SEM analysis was conducted using SmartPLS© (Ringle et al., 2024).

2.4. Predictive model for adoption intention

The predictive model for estimating farmers' adoption intention follows the linear additive approach of the TPB model (Sok et al., 2021). We assume that all six constructs directly shape and control behavioural intention on the basis of the direction and statistical significance of their path coefficients in the SEM:

$$AI = \beta_1(\overline{ATD}) + \beta_2(\overline{PBC}) + \beta_3(\overline{SN}) + \beta_4(\overline{PC}) + \beta_5(\overline{RA}) + \beta_6(\overline{PEU}) \quad (1)$$

where $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5,$ and β_6 are the respective estimated path coefficients of each construct of the sample.

To establish a threshold for predicting adoption intention, we computed the baseline adoption intention coefficient (BAIC) using the mean ranks of each construct generated from the 354 respondents, weighted by their path coefficients:

$$BAIC = \sum_{i=1}^6 w_i \bar{x}_i \quad (2)$$

where \bar{x}_i is the mean rank of construct i (ATD, PBC, SN, PC, RA, PEU) and where w_i is the weighted value of the respective constructs based on the path coefficients in the extended TPB results.

A new respondent's (target farmer) adoption intention score (AI_{new}) is calculated using Equation (1), which is based on the mean rank of the constructs, weighted by the standardized path coefficient values from the SEM. The computed AI_{new} is then compared to the baseline adoption intention coefficient (BAIC) to determine both the presence and level of adoption intention. If AI_{new} ≥ BAIC, the respondent is predicted to have an intention to adopt pesticide-reducing innovations.

For respondents predicted to have such an adoption intention, their adoption intention score (AI_{new}) is classified as low, moderate, or high based on its deviation from the sample mean using the standard deviation (σ) as an informative measure of variability (Carr et al., 1996). This approach assesses how far an individual's AI score deviates from the

average across the sample. Specifically, respondents with AI scores less than one standard deviation from the mean ($AI_{new} < BAIC - 1\sigma$) are classified as having low adoption intention, those within one standard deviation ($BAIC - 1\sigma \leq AI_{new} \leq BAIC + 1\sigma$) are categorized as having moderate adoption intention, and those more than one standard deviation ($AI_{new} > BAIC + 1\sigma$) are classified as having high adoption intention. The detailed empirical steps are presented in [Appendix D](#).

3. Results

3.1. Decision-making in the orchard sector

As a result of the semi-structured expert interviews, the study found that the decision-making process in orchard farms regarding pest and disease control is a complex, multistakeholder process shaped by farm size, ownership structure, and external actors. While farmers play a central role as either sole decision-makers or facilitators in smaller or self-owned farms, larger farms rely on collective processes involving managers, technicians, and directors. The process is also influenced by phytosanitary experts, commercial input suppliers, and sustainability considerations. These insights highlight the involvement of multiple actors and the interplay of several factors that together shape how decisions are made.

According to the experts, the main factors influencing the adoption of new practices and technologies were cost, efficacy, regulatory compliance, expert approval, and ease of use. Notably, 13 of the 16 experts identified cost as a major barrier, while 11 highlighted the importance of efficacy, underscoring that farmers evaluate new technologies in comparison to their existing methods. Furthermore, nine experts emphasized simplicity and ease of use, suggesting that farmers are more inclined to adopt innovations when they are easy to implement and compatible with current practices. These findings provide empirical justification for the inclusion of perceived cost, the relative advantage of existing methods, and perceived ease of use as additional constructs in the extended TPB model. A summary of the expert interviews is presented in [Table 2](#).

3.2. Descriptive analysis

[Table 3](#) presents the descriptive statistics for the constructs. Farmers expressed a strong overall intention to adopt pesticide-reducing innovations (INT, Mean = 6.00). Attitudes towards pesticide reduction were highly positive (ATD, Mean = 5.59), and subjective norms were also rated positively (SN, Mean = 5.35), suggesting considerable social and peer influence on farmers' decisions. Perceived behavioral control was moderate (PBC, Mean = 4.86), indicating partial confidence in their ability to adopt such practices. The perceptions of costs associated with implementing these innovations were also moderate (PC, Mean = 4.58), highlighting that financial concerns remain relevant. Farmers further reported moderate evaluations of the relative advantages of existing practices (RA, Mean = 3.09) and the perceived ease of use of alternatives (PEU, Mean = 4.48), reflecting mixed views on the comparative benefits and practical feasibility of pesticide-reducing innovations. In addition to descriptive statistics, [Table 3](#) also reports the reliability and validity statistics used to confirm the robustness of the measurement model.

3.3. Assessment of construct validity and model robustness

Convergent validity was first assessed using outer loadings and the average variance extracted (AVE). All retained measurement items exceeded the recommended threshold of 0.70 ([Leguina, 2015](#)), with the exception of three items (INT3, INT4, PEU4), which were removed in line with [Fornell and Larcker's \(1981\)](#) recommendation. The AVE values for all constructs surpassed the 0.50 benchmark ([Hair et al., 2019; Sarstedt et al., 2023](#)), and composite reliability (CR) values were above 0.70, confirming convergent validity and construct reliability.

Table 2
Insights from experts regarding decision-making about pest management.

Key questions	Main Findings	Observation remark
Who selects pesticides?	Farm managers, foremen, farmers, technical advisors, extension officers, salesmen, phytosanitary experts, government institutions, and commercial input companies	Depends on several factors such as farm size, ownership, associations and others.
Who decides whether a new treatment or technology is used in orchards?	Phytosanitary experts, farmers, managers, technicians, and directors.	Farmers' role depends on the farm size and ownership structure. Large farms: decisions made collectively by managers, technicians, and directors.
What roles do farmers play in the decision-making regarding new treatments or technology involving pest and disease control?	Farmers act as facilitators in trials, information agents or final decision-makers depending on the farm management structure.	Farmers are the main decision makers if they are the sole owners.
Factors influencing adoption decisions regarding pest and disease control technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cost of innovation - Efficacy of technology/better alternatives - Approval from technical experts - Meets EU regulatory requirements - Pressure from commercial companies - Evidence from trials or demonstrations - Sustainability and social conformity - Ease of use/less time consuming/simple 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 13 Experts 11 Expert 5 Experts 4 Experts 2 Experts 2 Experts 5 Experts 9 Experts
	TOTAL	16 Experts

Source: Expert survey conducted by authors

Discriminant validity was assessed using both the Fornell-Larcker criterion and the heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT). The square root of each construct's AVE was greater than its inter-construct correlations, and all HTMT values in [Appendix B](#) were below the conservative threshold of 0.85 ([Cheung et al., 2024; Henseler et al., 2015; Roemer et al., 2021](#)).

Finally, potential collinearity was examined through the variance inflation factor (VIF). The highest observed VIF was 2.851, well below the acceptable threshold of 3.0. This indicates that multicollinearity was not a concern and that each construct uniquely contributed to the model estimation ([Sarstedt et al., 2023](#)).

3.4. The structural equation model results

The findings of the structural relationship estimations are presented in [Fig. 3](#) with further details in [Table 4](#). The results indicate that attitudes had a significant positive effect on adoption intentions ($\beta = 0.623, p < 0.001$). In contrast, subjective norms ($\beta = 0.047, p > 0.10$) and perceived behavioral control ($\beta = 0.008, p > 0.10$) did not exhibit a significant influence. Consequently, [H1](#) was supported, whereas [H2](#) and [H3](#) were not. Additionally, both perceived cost ($\beta = -0.380, p > 0.001$) and the relative advantage of existing methods ($\beta = -0.191, p > 0.001$) had a negative impact on adoption intentions, confirming [H4](#) and [H5](#). Notably, perceived ease of use of pesticide-reducing innovations showed a positive relationship with adoption intentions ($\beta = 0.106, p < 0.05$), thereby supporting [H6](#).

The explanatory power of the model was assessed using the coefficient of determination (R^2) for adoption intention. The R^2 value was 0.432, indicating that the six constructs jointly explain 43 % of the

Table 3
Reliability, validity, and descriptive statistics of constructs.

Constructs	Loading	AVE	CR	VIF	Mean	SD	Mean interpretation
Adoption intention		0.911	0.954	–	6.00	1.386	High
INT1	0.955						
INT2	0.955						
INT3 ^D	–						
INT4 ^D	–						
Attitude towards pesticide use		0.582	0.848	2.032	5.59	1.171	High
ATD1	0.749						
ATD2	0.724						
ATD3	0.824						
ATD4	0.752						
Perceived behavioral control		0.808	0.894	2.531	4.86	1.812	Moderate
PBC1	0.899						
PBC2	0.899						
Subjective norms		0.650	0.847	2.323	5.35	1.396	High
SN1	0.856						
SN2	0.836						
SN3	0.720						
Perceived costs		0.912	0.954	2.851	4.58	1.923	Moderate
PC1	0.955						
PC2	0.955						
Relative advantage		0.798	0.922	1.575	3.09	1.733	Moderate
RA1	0.804						
RA2	0.931						
RA3	0.939						
RA4 ^D	–						
Perceived ease of use		0.647	0.880	1.483	4.48	1.786	Moderate
PEU1	0.820						
PEU2	0.781						
PEU3	0.805						
PEU4	0.809						

INT: Intention to adopt pesticide reducing innovation; ATD: Attitude towards the use of pesticide; PBC: Perceived behavioral control; SN: Subjective norms; PC: Perceived cost; RA: Relative advantage of existing methods; PEU: Perceived ease of use of pesticide-reducing innovations; D: Item dropped due its low loading CR: Composite reliability; AVE: Average variance extracted; SD: Standard deviation and VIF: Variance inflation factor. Mean score interpretation: 1–2.99 = Low; 3.00–5.00 = Moderate; 5.01–7.00 = High.

variance in farmers' adoption intentions. According to Hair et al. (2011), this represents moderate explanatory power and is comparable to the 39 % average reported in a TPB meta-analysis by Armitage and Conner (2001) as well as to ranges observed in more recent reviews (Steinmetz et al., 2016; McDermott et al., 2015). Similar outcomes have also been reported in extended TPB models, such as that used by Baishakhy et al. (2025), who found 24 % for the baseline TPB and 32 % with six additional constructs. In addition, the predictive relevance of our model is supported by the Q^2 value of 0.412, which is well above the zero threshold and indicates strong predictive capability (Sarstedt et al., 2022).

3.5. The adoption intention predictive tool

Based on the structural equation results of the extended TPB, we developed the adoption intention predictive tool (AIPT), a web-based framework using the stepwise computation framework detailed in section 2.2 and Appendix D. Thus, the AIPT is based on the 18 measurement items of the six constructs - ATD, PBC, SN, PC, RA, and PEU - which are hypothesized to directly predict adoption intention. The constructs were weighted on the basis of their significance and the size of the estimated path coefficients. Non-significant constructs such as PBC and SN were normalized to near zero, making their impact on the predictive model less significant.

Depending on an individual's response to the 18 measurement items, the AIPT predicts whether they have no, low, moderate or high adoption intention with regard to pesticide-reducing technologies based on the computational algorithm involving the six constructs used in this study. Fig. 4 provides an overview of the AIPT tool, showcasing the initial landing page and the results page displayed after users complete their responses to the 18 indicator items. The tool can be accessed from the link: <https://designer.spreadsheetweb.com/a/adoption-tool>.

4. Discussion and implication

4.1. Discussion of the findings

The findings of this study contribute to advancing our knowledge of farmers' acceptance and intention to adopt emerging pesticide-reducing innovations. Specifically, our findings indicate that decision-making regarding pest and disease treatment on orchard farms is complex and involves multiple factors and stakeholders. Farmers have different roles to play in this process, depending on farm size and ownership structure. Farmers' attitudes and perceived ease of use of pesticide-reducing innovations strengthen their intention to adopt them, while perceived cost and the belief that existing methods offer a relative advantage remain major barriers. These insights have important implications for policy and practice, highlighting the need for targeted incentives, knowledge-sharing initiatives, and support mechanisms to accelerate the transition toward sustainable pest management to meet EU pesticide reduction targets.

Our results highlight the need for broader stakeholder engagement in order to achieve pesticide reduction targets in the orchard sector. Previous studies on pesticide reduction efforts and adoption drivers have often treated farmers as the sole decision makers (Bakker et al., 2021; Chèze et al., 2020). However, our findings show that decision-making with regard to pest and disease management could extend beyond farmers, with commercial pesticide suppliers and other stakeholders also playing influential roles. This aligns with the finding of Heitkampfer et al. (2023), who reported that the success of new digital technologies that reduce pesticides depends not only on farmers but also on the enthusiasm of farm managers, as well as on public and consumer support. Therefore, effective strategies to promote synthetic pesticide reduction should not only target farmers but also foster coordinated action across the value chain, ensuring that farmers, suppliers, advisors,

Fig. 3. Overview of the model estimates.

Note: Standardized path coefficients with corresponding p-values are shown on each path. Arrow thickness reflects the relative strength of the relationships. Detailed results, including bootstrapped t-values are provided in Table.

Table 4
Structural relationships.

Hypothesis	β	t-value	p-value
H1: Attitudes → Adoption intentions	0.623***	7.649	0.000
H2: Subjective norms → Adoption intentions	0.047	0.613	0.270
H3: Perceived behavioral control → Adoption intentions	0.008	0.099	0.461
H4: Perceived cost → Adoption intentions	-0.380***	4.493	0.000
H5: Relative advantage of existing methods → Adoption intentions	-0.191***	3.356	0.000
H6: Perceived ease of use of innovations → Adoption intentions	0.106**	1.816	0.035

β = Path coefficient; VIF=Variance inflation factor; Significance level of path coefficient = * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

and all concerned stakeholders are jointly engaged in shaping and sustaining adoption decisions (Meunier et al., 2024; Möhring et al., 2020).

With regard to the predictors of farmers' adoption intentions with regard to pesticide-reducing innovation, the results show that attitude towards pesticide reduction is the most important predictor of farmers' adoption intentions (H1 is supported). In essence, farmers with positive attitudes toward pesticide reduction are more likely to adopt pesticide-reducing technologies. This finding aligns with those of Sok et al. (2024), who reported that farmers' attitudes are becoming increasingly important in terms of shaping their aspirations to reduce pesticide use. Consequently, fostering positive attitudes is crucial for driving the

adoption and diffusion of pesticide-reducing innovations in the EU orchard sector (Garmendia-Lemus et al., 2024). However, while attitude emerges as the strongest predictor, it alone may not be sufficient to drive adoption without considering other equally important factors. For example, a meta-analysis of technology adoption by Neves et al. (2022) identified perceived benefits, personal awareness, knowledge, and incentives as additional key influences on farmers' decisions. This highlights the need for a holistic approach that not only reinforces positive attitudes, but also integrates economic and informational support to drive real adoption rates.

As expected, perceived cost emerged as a significant barrier to adoption intentions (H4 supported). The findings show that when farmers anticipate high financial or practical burdens, their willingness to adopt pesticide-reducing innovations decreases. This outcome is consistent with PMT, which posits that high response costs weaken coping appraisal and reduce the motivation to act. Comparable evidence has been reported in other contexts, such as the negative effect of costs on the uptake of mobile farming applications (Okoroji et al., 2021). Conversely, studies indicate that reducing response costs through targeted training, streamlined regulation, or economic incentives can strengthen adoption intentions (Aung et al., 2025; Li et al., 2023). These results highlight the importance of policy measures that improve the financial accessibility of pesticide-reducing innovations, for example by easing regulatory burdens, supporting cooperative procurement, or providing training, in order to encourage wider adoption.

Interestingly, our analysis shows that the perceived relative advantage of existing pest management methods over pesticide-reducing

Adoption Intention Predictive Tool (AIPT)
A predictive tool based on the Theory of Planned Behavior

Welcome to the AIPT platform!

The **AIPT** is designed to predict farmers' intention to adopt emerging pesticide-reducing technologies in the vineyard and olive grove sectors. The tool consist of **18 statements** covering attitude, subjective norm, behavioral control, perceived cost, effectiveness of current methods and familiarity with **alternative innovations** aimed at **reducing** pesticide use.

To participate, kindly consider each statement carefully and indicate the extent to which you **AGREE** or **DISAGREE**. Completing this will take approximately **4 to 8** minutes of your time and you will be able to see your **AIPT** result at the end.

The AIPT Results
A predictive tool based on the Theory of Planned Behavior

Based on your responses to the statements, the AIPT predicts based on the Theory of Planned Behavior that you have **HIGH INTENTION** to adopt pesticide-reducing innovations in your farm.

Fig. 4. Overview of the adoption intention predictive tool (AIPT).

innovations significantly predicts farmers' adoption intentions, supporting H5. Thus, farmers who view their current methods as comparatively effective are less inclined to adopt new approaches, perhaps due to concerns about potential losses from untested technologies. Previous research confirms that higher risk perceptions reduce farmers' willingness to change established practices (Chèze et al., 2020; Liu and Liu, 2024). This highlights the difficulty of shifting deeply-trusted methods, especially when the perceived benefits or reliability of alternatives remain uncertain (Bakker et al., 2022). Our results also suggest that self-efficacy plays a role: farmers with strong confidence in their current pest control strategies are less motivated to adopt conservation-oriented innovations (Savari et al., 2023). Addressing these barriers will require clear demonstrations of the practical effectiveness of emerging pesticide-reducing technologies, including field trials, transparent cost-benefit analyses, and targeted training. Ultimately, providing convincing evidence of long-term yield stability, cost savings, and environmental gains could be essential as a means of building trust and accelerating adoption among orchard farmers.

Moreover, perceived ease of use with regard to pesticide-reducing innovations was found to significantly influence farmers' intentions to adopt them, supporting H6. This suggests that when farmers view these technologies as simple and practical to incorporate into their existing routines, they are more inclined to adopt them. This finding is consistent with De Canio (2023), who highlights the role of pro-environmental familiarity, farmers' confidence and knowledge in managing environmental challenges, in shaping adoption decisions. Similar patterns have been observed in previous studies, which emphasize the importance of direct exposure and hands-on experience. For instance, Yigezu et al. (2018) found that field demonstrations and offering first-time users free access to technologies significantly increased both the speed and extent of adoption. In line with this, the present results suggest that building farmers' capacity through practical engagement could enhance their intention to adopt pesticide-reducing innovations. In essence, these findings point to the value of well-structured support programs. Demonstration trials, targeted training, and improved access can help raise awareness, build trust, and ultimately encourage broader adoption

of sustainable practices among orchard farmers.

Our results show that neither subjective norms nor perceived behavioral control significantly influenced farmers' intentions to adopt pesticide-reducing innovations (H2 and H3 not supported). This suggests that peer influence and perceived ability to adopt these innovations did not drive adoption intentions. Such findings diverge from the core assumptions of the TPB and from many studies where these constructs have been significant predictors of intention. For example, Mustapa et al. (2024) reported perceived behavioral control as the most significant factor influencing purchasing intention with regard to plant-based products, while Suntornsan et al. (2022) identified subjective norms as the strongest predictor of energy-saving intentions.

Nevertheless, previous research also shows that the predictive strength of TPB constructs can vary across contexts. Bozionelos and Bennett (1999) found that both subjective norms and attitude toward exercise were not significant predictors of exercise intention, while Herath (2013) reported that subjective norms did not significantly influence farmers' adoption behavior. Similarly, Zhao et al. (2022) demonstrated that perceived behavioral control was not a significant predictor of intentions to participate in agritourism. These findings highlight that the influence of TPB constructs is highly context-dependent, and contingent on the specific type of behavioral intention examined.

In our case, several contextual factors may explain the non-significance of subjective norms and perceived behavioral control. Regarding subjective norms, one explanation lies in the growing recognition that alternative forms of norms are rarely tested in TPB but increasingly emphasized in recent studies. These include descriptive norms (perceptions of how common a behavior is) and personal norms (internalized standards at the individual level rather than those imposed by social groups). Niemiec et al. (2020) found that when personal and descriptive norms are strong within a group, the effect of subjective norms on intentions is substantially reduced. In the case of orchard farmers, pest management practices are deeply rooted, often passed down through generations, and reinforced by tradition. In such contexts, personal norms may dominate decision-making, reducing the role of

social pressure. Moreover, farms managed independently or within diverse production systems may further limit the relevance of peer influence. The educational profile of the farmers in our sample may also contribute to this pattern, as farmers with higher education levels or greater access to technical information may rely more on their own expertise and less on peer endorsement. This interpretation is consistent with the findings of Li et al. (2023), who found that government promotion and institutional support had a stronger influence on farmers' willingness to adopt smart agricultural technologies than peer networks or social reference groups.

For perceived behavioral control, the non-significance may reflect the balance between its two components: self-efficacy (confidence in one's ability to perform a behavior) and controllability (perceptions of external constraints) (Ajzen, 2002). While farmers may feel confident in their personal ability to adopt pesticide-reducing innovations, external barriers such as high costs, regulatory complexity, and technical requirements appear to overshadow this confidence. As a result, the overall predictive power of perceived behavioral control is weakened, with external limitations outweighing internal efficacy.

Finally, our AIPT tool provides a valuable framework for scaling our findings beyond the study sample to orchard farmers across all EU member states. While previous adoption prediction tools such as the one developed by Kuehne et al. (2017), provided valuable insights into farmers' uptake of new agricultural practices, they had a broad scope, incorporating 22 variables without a strong theoretical foundation. In contrast, the AIPT is specifically designed for the orchard sector and is firmly grounded in established theory, making it more streamlined, easy to apply, and interpret. By focusing on pesticide-reducing innovations in the orchard sector, the AIPT offers a targeted and precise prediction of farmers' adoption intentions. This sector-specific approach enhances its practical relevance, providing policymakers and stakeholders with farmers' behavioral insights that could complement other scientific research methods and tools essential for data-driven decisions.

4.2. Theoretical implications

This study advances the theoretical development of the TPB by extending its framework with three additional constructs: perceived cost, relative advantage of existing practices, and perceived ease of use of pesticide-reducing innovations. The findings confirm that while attitude remains the strongest predictor of farmers' adoption intentions, perceived cost and the relative advantage of established practices act as significant barriers. By contrast, the non-significance of subjective norms and perceived behavioral control suggests that the predictive strength of TPB components is highly context-dependent, as anticipated by Ajzen (1991). In orchard farming, adoption decisions appear to be shaped less by social influence or perceived ability, and more by economic and experiential considerations. This helps explain the moderate explanatory power of the extended TPB model ($R^2 = 0.432$). Although this level of variance is consistent with meta-analyses of TPB applications (Armitage and Conner, 2001; Steinmetz et al., 2016), it also indicates that a substantial share of farmers' adoption intentions remains unexplained. These findings highlight the importance of adapting the TPB to sector-specific contexts and to complementing it with additional constructs or mediators that capture structural and contextual influences, thereby enhancing its explanatory capacity in agricultural innovation research.

The development of AIPT represents an innovative methodological contribution, offering a dynamic application of behavioral intention models with regard to real-world decision-making. This enhances the utility of TPB beyond academic research, providing policymakers and industry stakeholders with a practical tool for assessing adoption likelihood among farmers.

Furthermore, this study contributes to behavioral economics by showing that perceived ease of use of innovations significantly shapes adoption intentions. The findings are consistent with the Mere Exposure

Effect, which suggests that greater familiarity increases the acceptance of new ideas and technologies (Bornstein and Craver-Lemley, 2022). By incorporating this psychological mechanism into the TPB framework, the study strengthens the link between agricultural technology adoption theories and behavioral psychology, providing a more nuanced understanding of farmers' decision-making processes.

Finally, this research contributes to the wider debate on sustainable agricultural transitions by showing that farmers' perceptions of the relative advantage of their existing pest control methods acts as a deterrent to adopting pesticide-reducing innovations. When current practices are viewed as more effective or reliable, farmers have little incentive to change, reinforcing the persistence of established routines. This finding underlines the need to account for past experiences and entrenched behavioral patterns when designing policies or interventions intended to encourage sustainable farming practices.

4.3. Practical implications

The findings of this study provide valuable insights for policymakers, agricultural technology developers, extension services, and industry stakeholders seeking to accelerate the adoption of pesticide-reducing innovations in the orchard sector. Since perceived cost is a key barrier to adoption, practical measures that improve the financial accessibility of pesticide-reducing innovations are essential. These may include easing administrative burdens, promoting cooperative purchasing schemes, and expanding access to low-cost training and advisory services. Such approaches can be particularly helpful for small and medium-sized farms that face greater challenges in covering initial investment costs. To support more inclusive and widespread adoption, these measures should be embedded within broader agricultural sustainability programs that enhance both feasibility and long-term engagement.

Another key implication concerns farmers' perceptions of the relative advantage of their existing pest control methods, which act as a barrier to adopting pesticide-reducing technologies. Alongside perceived costs, this barrier is driven by uncertainty and risk perception, as many farmers believe that their current approaches are more reliable or cost-effective than emerging alternatives. Addressing these concerns requires clear, evidence-based demonstrations of the benefits of pesticide-reducing technologies. Strategies such as field trials, detailed cost-benefit analyses, peer-to-peer knowledge exchange, and farmer field schools could help illustrate the long-term agronomic and economic advantages of these innovations. Building trust through demonstrable success stories is therefore essential to challenge entrenched reliance on conventional practices and to strengthen confidence in sustainable pest management solutions.

The role of education and training programs could also be crucial in fostering adoption. Since perceived ease of use of pesticide-reducing innovations positively influences farmers' adoption intentions, policymakers and industry stakeholders should invest in targeted knowledge dissemination initiatives. On-farm training, digital extension platforms, and interactive workshops can enhance farmers' understanding of how to integrate the emerging pesticide-reducing technologies into their production systems. The AIPT developed in this study presents a practical opportunity for tailoring outreach strategies. By identifying farmers with higher adoption potential, policymakers and extension services can develop customized support programs that address specific barriers and knowledge gaps.

Additionally, the study highlights the complexity of decision-making in orchard farming, which extends beyond individual farmers to technical advisors, input suppliers, and regulatory bodies. This finding reinforces the need for a multi-stakeholder approach to pesticide reduction efforts. Stronger collaboration between research institutions, agricultural cooperatives, policymakers, and industry stakeholders is essential for facilitating the transition to sustainable pest and disease management in orchards. The integration of advisory services,

cooperative purchasing models, and supply chain incentives could ensure that the adoption of pesticide-reducing innovations aligns with broader market and regulatory demands.

Overall, these insights highlight the urgency of developing policies and support mechanisms that address both economic and behavioral barriers to adoption. The transition to sustainable pest management requires a combination of financial incentives, capacity-building initiatives, and coordinated industry engagement. By fostering positive attitudes toward pesticide reduction, improving education on emerging innovations, and alleviating cost-related concerns, policymakers and stakeholders can help accelerate adoption among conventional orchard farmers. These efforts are likely to be most effective when embedded within broader agroecological transitions. Recent studies underscore the importance of structural enablers such as access to training, financial resources, and farmer networks (Alphonse et al., 2024; Ataei et al., 2023), while also highlighting the influence of ecological values and life experiences in motivating long-term change (Markiewicz-Keszycka et al., 2025). Building on these insights, policy frameworks should align the promotion of pesticide-reducing innovations with measures that reduce financial risks, expand technical support, and foster collaborative learning environments. Such an integrated approach not only facilitates technology adoption but also strengthens the resilience and long-term sustainability of vineyard and olive production systems.

4.4. Limitations and future research

Despite the valuable insights provided by this study, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the study assumes homogeneity among orchard farmers regarding pest control activities. In reality, factors such as weather conditions, production systems, and farm management practices may create both apparent and subtle differences in decision-making, ultimately influencing attitudes, perceptions, and the practical implementation of these innovations.

Second, although our analysis found no significant differences in the mean ranking of the constructs between vineyard and olive farmers (see Appendix C), future research with larger datasets could investigate whether distinct subgroups exist. A more granular approach backed by large data samples, such as segmentation analysis, might yield deeper insights into potential variations among orchard farmers.

Third, although the sampling strategy allowed us to reach a diverse group of vineyard and olive farmers across five countries, it relied on stakeholder events and network diffusion. While such approaches are common in farmer-based studies where populations are geographically dispersed, they may limit the generalizability of the findings beyond the study sample. Our results should therefore be interpreted as representative of the participating farmers rather than all European orchard farmers. Future research could strengthen external validity by employing probability-based sampling or larger-scale surveys designed to reduce potential selection bias.

Furthermore, in order to provide a broad overview of farmers' adoption intentions, this study assumes that all emerging pesticide-reducing innovations are equally applicable across orchard farms. However, in reality, the suitability of these innovations varies, depending on factors such as farm size, topography, and management practices, requiring caution when generalizing the findings. For instance, orchard farms in mountainous terrains may face limitations when it comes to adopting robotic technologies for site-specific weed management due to operational constraints. Despite this limitation, the adoption intention predictive tool offers flexibility, allowing future studies and applications to be tailored to specific technologies, ensuring more precise adoption predictions.

Lastly, the extended TPB was estimated without moderating factors in order to streamline the model and support the development of a predictive tool. This decision enhanced parsimony and transparency, but may have overlooked potential indirect influences. Future research could build on this framework by incorporating socio-demographic,

economic, and contextual moderators to capture additional variance in adoption intentions. While such extensions would increase complexity, they could also provide a more nuanced understanding of subgroup differences and yield sharper insights for targeted policy design.

5. Conclusions

This study provides crucial insights into orchard farmers' adoption intentions with regard to pesticide-reducing innovations, directly supporting the previous EU Green Deal targets to halve pesticide use by 2030. Overall, the results indicate that orchard farmers exhibit a strong intention to adopt pesticide-reducing innovations, with attitude emerging as the strongest predictor of adoption intention. Moreover, farmers' perceptions of the ease of use of pesticide-reducing innovations significantly increases their intention to adopt, while perceived costs and the belief that their existing methods have higher relative advantage limit their adoption intentions. Importantly, decisions on pest and disease management do not rest solely with farmers but involve network of stakeholders including technical advisors, input suppliers, and regulatory bodies, highlighting the importance of engaging a wider set of actors in pesticide reduction strategies. The results suggest that achieving meaningful reductions in synthetic pesticide use requires more than simply making new technologies available. A coordinated approach, supported by policies that remove economic and technical barriers, foster positive attitudes toward pesticide reduction, and clearly demonstrate practical benefits, is essential to encourage widespread adoption within conventional orchard farming. Specifically, efforts must include incentives to offset initial costs, targeted training programs to build technical capacity, on-farm demonstrations to showcase effectiveness and advantages, and tailored information campaigns to improve awareness and perception of pesticide-reducing innovations.

With the European Commission's proposed legislation failing to gain political and farmer support, this study provides a valuable understanding of the factors that could drive the voluntary adoption of pesticide-reducing innovations in the orchard sector. Our findings emphasize the need for a holistic approach that considers not only farmers, but also other key actors when it comes to influencing pesticide-use decisions.

In the case of policymakers, the findings highlight the need for measures that improve the financial accessibility of pesticide-reducing innovations, such as easing regulatory burdens, supporting cooperative procurement models, and integrating practical training into extension services. Knowledge-sharing platforms and farmer-led demonstration initiatives can further strengthen trust, build hands-on familiarity, and shift attitudes toward more sustainable practices. In parallel, to support broader adoption, agri-tech and innovation developers should focus on creating solutions that are cost-effective, context-specific, and easy to integrate into existing farm systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Noah Larvoe: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Muhammad Adzran Che Mustapa:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Felicidad de Herralde:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Zein Kallas:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2025.107460>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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